

COLLEGE STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES ON DANCE EXERCISES

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) of college students toward dance exercises, particularly focusing on Philippine folk dance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard), within the Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT 002) subject. Using a descriptive-quantitative design, data were collected from 301 students at the University of La Salette, Inc., through a validated and pilot-tested questionnaire. Findings showed that 49.5% of students had adequate knowledge of Philippine folk dance, and 35.5% had adequate knowledge of social dances. However, a significant percentage lacked an in-depth understanding, especially in social dances. Attitudes were highly positive, with mean scores of 3.50 for folk dances and 3.42 for social dances, reflecting appreciation for dance as a cultural and physical activity. Despite this, practice levels were only practiced often ($M=2.92$ for folk dance, $M=2.75$ for social dances), indicating a gap between what students know and how often they engage in dance. To address this gap, the study proposes the PATHFIT Program—Promoting Active Training and Holistic Fitness (PATHFIT) through Interactive Dance Exercises—as an intervention to foster consistent, enjoyable, and culturally relevant dance participation among students. The results offer insights for physical education instructors and policymakers aiming to enhance student engagement, fitness, and cultural appreciation.

Keywords: *Dance Exercise, Philippine Folk Dance, Social Dances, KAP*

INTRODUCTION

Most people aspire to lead a healthy life. Attaining a certain level of health is essential. Engaging in regular physical activity or exercise is one way to accomplish this. Any exercise designed, organized, and performed continuously to achieve physical fitness is called physical exercise. In contrast, physical activity refers to any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure. Physical and/or bodily exercise is voluntary, planned, repetitive physical activity to maintain or improve fitness and health (Lieberman, 2021). According to the Global Action Plan on Physical Activity (WHO,2018), over 80% of adolescents do not meet the recommended daily activity levels, and this trend often continues until students reach their college journey.

Dance is perceived both as exercise and as something that moves beyond exercise. A humanistic aspect to dance may be missing from other forms of exercise that participants value (Elmslie et al.,2025). Dance Fitness is a fun way to increase cardiovascular endurance, strength, and flexibility. A wide variety of dance genres support fitness. Dance-related fitness training systems, such as cardio dance, barre workouts, and other dance fitness forms, have significantly increased in popularity over the last few decades. Millions of people enjoy using dance as a fitness activity (Kassing, 2024). In this context, dance has emerged as a promising form of physical activity that can promote engagement and improve health outcomes (Štambuk , Tomičić ,2021).

Latin dance has been demonstrated to promote physical health by helping people lose weight, improve cardiovascular health, increase muscle strength and tone, and improve flexibility and balance. Furthermore, Latin dance can benefit mental health by reducing stress, improving mood, social connection, and cognitive function (Liu et al., 2023).

Dance is a unique form of exercise that is often accessible and modifiable according to the individual's cultural background and physical abilities. It can increase physical activity levels by creating social engagement. Limited data from intervention studies with small sample sizes and short duration or follow-up suggested that routine participation in dance can improve agility and balance, leading to decreased rates of immobility and depression, which may act as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease. It may also assist with blood pressure control in patients with hypertension. (Tatavarthy & Oktay, 2025; Isath et al.,2023).

To promote wellness and fitness and reduce physical inactivity among college students, tertiary education institutions have adopted Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFit) as a core course. This course aims to instill knowledge, appreciation, and practice of various physical activities, including dance exercises, as part of the holistic development of the students. Dance exercise is a feasible alternative to traditional physical activity. Also, dance provides physiological and psychological benefits to healthy and medically compromised populations (Tao et al.,2022).

To maximize the impact of dance exercise in the PATHFIT course, it is crucial to understand the students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP). The KAP model has been popular, especially in the field of public health, where it helps provide valuable information for resource allocation in the planning and implementation of public health programs (Andrade et al., 2020). Additionally, KAP is applied to areas such as disease prevention (Di Gennaro et al., 2024), immunization (Iqbal et al., 2025), and hygiene (Saleh & Chedid, 2025). KAP models are increasingly being adapted to other disciplines, including physical activity (Butt et al., 2025), diet (Singh et al., 2025), and exercise (Alagappan et al., 2022). However, most KAP-based studies in physical education still focus on exercises in general (Mohd et al., 2023), physical activity (Kandasamy et al., 2024), sports, and nutrition (Muhamad, 2021).

Studies on folk dance education indicate positive outcomes for students' personal development, cultural identity, health and emotional regulation (Chen, 2023). However, awareness and exposure remain limited. Javina (2021) found moderate awareness among students regarding the objectives, strategies, skills, and training in Philippine folk dances, with limited actual dance experience. Lobo (2022) reported that Bachelor of Physical Education and Bachelor of Performing Arts programs had only average experience with traditional dances, but expressed interest in learning more about dance history, costumes, and meanings. Similarly, Reyes et al. (2020) observed that insufficient exposure led to limited understanding and appreciation of folk dances. Monte (2025) further emphasized that participation in the Philippine folk dances fosters greater appreciation of Filipino heritage, identity, and cultural storytelling. Practical exposure was found to strongly correlate with students' interest and engagement, and structured dance programs are recommended to enhance learning and appreciation.

Regarding attitudes toward exercises, several studies report generally positive perspectives. Mohamed et al. (2022), Sharma et al. (2023), and Maduakolam et al. (2023) noted that both active and inactive students of both genders exhibited moderately positive attitudes.

Hsu, Lin, and Shang (2023) highlighted that students' attitudes toward dance exercises are strongly influenced by enjoyment, engagement, and cultural connection, and that interactive sessions in physical education foster motivation and positive perspective.

Despite these positive attitudes, barriers such as academic stress, tight schedules, and undervaluation of physical activity often impede consistent participation (Moore et al., 2023). Liu et al. (2021) emphasized that university Pe programs play a key role in fostering holistic student development by integrating physical activity into students' lifestyles.

Furthermore, reviewed studies focus on either student interest or performance outcomes in dance (Lobo, 2022; Javina, 2021). Few, if any, explore the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) of students on dance as exercise in terms of Philippine Folkdance and Social Dance (Latin and Standard) among college students and as

practiced in the PATHFIT course. This presents a gap in both literature and practice. Therefore, the study is deemed necessary to assess the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of college students at the University of La Salette Incorporated toward dance exercise in the context of Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness, particularly in terms of Philippine Folkdance and Social Dance (Latin and Standard). This study will provide data for curriculum development, student engagement strategies, and cultural integration in physical education.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of knowledge on dance exercises of college students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Philippine Folkdance
 - 1.2 Social Dances (Latin and Standard)
2. What is the attitude on dance exercises of college students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Philippine Folkdance
 - 2.2 Social Dances (Latin and Standard)
3. What is the practice on dance exercises of college students in terms of:
 - 3.1 Philippine Folkdance
 - 3.2 Social Dances (Latin and Standard)
4. What measures can be proposed to enhance college students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices on dance exercises (Philippine Folkdance and Social Dances)?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at the University of La Salette, Inc., located in Dubinan East, Santiago City, Isabela. The participants are college students enrolled in Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) 002 subject for the second semester of the academic year 2024-2025.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Method

The population for this study consisted of 1,371 students enrolled in the Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) 002 subject across various colleges at the University of La Salette, Incorporated, for the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year. The students were divided into strata based on their college/department (e.g., CAS, CBE, CEA, CTE, etc.). Each department/college serves as a distinct stratum. The stratified sampling method ensures that each department is adequately represented in the sample. The sample sizes for each stratum are determined based on the total number of students in each group to maintain proportionality. A sample size of 301 was computed using a Raosoft calculator with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. The distribution of participants is shown below.

Department	Population	Sample Size
College of Arts and Sciences	80	18
College of Business Education	235	52
College of Teacher Education	43	9
College of Information Technology	60	13
College of Medicine and Allied Medical Program	245	54
College of Nursing Public Health and Midwifery	339	74
College of Engineering and Architecture	280	61
College of Accountancy	89	20
Total	1371	301

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher adhered to the necessary ethical and institutional research protocols—the data gathering procedure commenced by securing formal approval from the University President to conduct the study. Data collection was through an online survey using Google Forms. The researcher coordinated with the PATHFIT 002 University instructors to assist in disseminating the research instrument. The instructors were requested to send the Google Forms link to their official group chats. Before answering the questionnaire, participants were provided with an informed consent letter outlining the purpose, their rights, and their voluntary participation in the study.

As data collection was conducted online, responses were automatically recorded through Google Forms. Once the required number of responses based on the calculated sample sizes was reached, the raw data were exported to Microsoft Excel. The data set underwent a data cleaning process to ensure accuracy and consistency. Data coding was carried out to organize the responses for analysis systematically.

Research Instrument

The researcher developed the questionnaire based on the course outcomes of the Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) 002 as implemented in the university, ensuring its relevance to the study's objectives. Upon completion of the initial draft, the questionnaire was reviewed by a grammarian. The grammarian assessed the instrument to ensure adherence to proper guidelines and mechanics in questionnaire development. Minor grammatical revisions were made following the review.

Five experts checked the validity of the questionnaire and conducted a deep analysis of each item. They provided feedback on the clarity of the questions, ensuring that they accurately assessed the intended concepts. The researcher consolidated the comments/suggestions and then edited, refined, and finalized them as suggested by the expert. Using a content validity tool, the researcher-made questionnaire received a validity index score of 0.98, indicating that it is a valid tool for the study.

Following the content validation, pilot testing was conducted among students enrolled in Physical Activities Towards Health and Fitness (PATHFIT) 004. A total of 30 respondents were randomly selected from various colleges within the university. The reliability of the test was calculated using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20). The knowledge on the dance exercises component of the questionnaire yielded a reliability score of 0.870. Meanwhile, the attitude and practice of dance exercises yielded Cronbach's Alpha scores of 0.886 and 0.953, respectively, indicating high internal consistency and reliability.

The questionnaire is composed of three sections. The first section focuses on Knowledge of Dance Exercises, which includes 10 items assessing students' knowledge of Philippine folk dances and another 10 items for social dances (Latin and Standard). The questions were derived from the topics and core concepts covered under PATHFIT 002.

The second section measures Attitude on Dance Exercises, consisting of 5 items related to folk dances and five related to social dances. The third and final section evaluates Practice on Dance Exercises, which includes seven items covering Philippine folk dances and another seven items covering Social Dances. The statements in these sections were adapted and modified from the studies of Kandasamy et al. (2024), titled "Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Towards Physical Activity among Healthcare Students at a Public University in Saudi Arabia," and Alagappan et al. (2022), titled "Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Exercise among Physiotherapy Students. These items were carefully revised and contextualized to suit the specific focus and objectives of the study.

Data Analysis

To interpret and give meaning to the data gathered in the study, the researcher utilized the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software and MS Excel. For the Level of Knowledge of college students on Dance Exercises, frequency and percentage were used to determine the level of knowledge regarding dance exercises. The mean was used for the Attitude and Practice on Dance Exercises to identify the general trends and levels of agreement or participation among the respondents.

A 4-point scale was used to analyze the interpretation of the students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding dance exercises.

Level Knowledge on Dance Exercise

Score	Knowledge Level	Descriptor
0 – 2	Minimal Knowledge	Very limited understanding; unable to explain or apply concepts accurately.
3 – 5	Basic Knowledge	Has surface-level understanding; can recall some facts but lacks application.

6 –8	Adequate Knowledge	Understands core concepts; can explain and apply knowledge in familiar contexts.
9 – 10	Superior Knowledge	Demonstrates in-depth understanding and can apply knowledge critically and effectively in various situations.

Attitudes on Dance Exercise

	Range	Attitude	Descriptor
1	1-1.74	Very Limited Positive Attitude	Consistently exhibits a negative attitude toward aerobic exercise
2	1.75-2.49	Developing Positive Attitude	Rarely exhibits a positive attitude and often shows indifference
3	2.50-3.24	Moderately Positive Attitude	Frequently exhibits a positive attitude with occasional reservations
4	3.25-4	Highly Positive Attitude	Consistently exhibits a highly positive attitude toward dance exercises, showing strong enthusiasm and value

Practice Dance Exercise

	Range	Practice	Descriptor
1	1-1.74	Never Practiced	Never engages in aerobic exercise or avoids it entirely
2	1.75-2.49	Sometimes Practiced	Occasionally engages in dance exercise.
3	2.50-3.24	Often Practiced	Frequently engages in dance exercise.
4	3.25-4	Always Practiced	Regularly and consistently engages in dance exercises.

RESULTS

This section presents the analyzed data concerning the study's research questions. Results are organized in tables, followed by corresponding interpretation and statistical analyses.

Part 1. Level of Knowledge on Dance Exercises in Terms of Philippine Folkdance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

Table 1

Distribution of the Students According to their Level of Knowledge on Dance Exercises in terms of Philippine Folkdance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

Philippine Folkdance	Frequency	Percentage
Minimal Knowledge	11	3.70
Basic Knowledge	63	20.9
Adequate Knowledge	149	49.5
Superior Knowledge	78	25.9
Social Dances (Latin and Standard)	Frequency	Percentage
Minimal Knowledge	42	14.0
Basic Knowledge	76	25.2
Adequate Knowledge	107	35.5
Superior Knowledge	76	25.2

Table 1 presents the distribution of college students based on their knowledge of dance exercises, in terms of Philippine folk dance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard).

Regarding Philippine folk dance, most students, 149 (49.5%), demonstrated adequate knowledge. This is followed by 78 (25.9%) students who have superior knowledge, 63 (20.9%) students with basic knowledge, and 11 (3.7%) students with minimal knowledge.

Regarding Social Dances (Latin and Standard), 107 (35.5%) students reported having adequate knowledge. An equal number of students, 76 (25.2%), possess superior and basic knowledge, respectively. Meanwhile, 42 students (14.0%) were found to have minimal knowledge.

Part 2. The Attitudes of College Students on Dance Exercises

2.1 Philippine Folkdance

Table 2

Attitudes on Dance Exercises in terms of Philippine Folk Dance

	Attitude On Dance Exercises (Folkdance)	Mean	Interpretation
1	I enjoy watching performances of Philippine folk dances.	3.48	Highly Positive Attitude
2	I believe folk dancing is an important part of our culture.	3.55	Highly Positive Attitude

3	I feel proud when I perform or see others perform folk dances.	3.51	Highly Positive Attitude
4	I consider folk dancing a valuable form of physical activity.	3.49	Highly Positive Attitude
5	I believe performing folk dances helps improve physical health and fitness.	3.49	Highly Positive Attitude
Category Mean		3.50	Highly Positive Attitude

Table 2 presents that the respondents have highly positive attitude in Dance exercises specifically in Philippine folkdance as indicated in the following statements: I believe folk dancing is an important part of our culture (M= 3.55); I feel proud when I perform or see others perform folk dances (M = 3.51); I consider folk dancing a valuable form of physical activity (M = 3.49); I believe performing folk dances helps improve physical health and fitness.(M = 3.49) I enjoy watching performances of Philippine folk dances (M = 3.48). With a category mean of 3.50, this implies that students demonstrate a highly positive attitude toward dance exercise, specifically Philippine folk dance.

2.2 Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

Table 3
Attitude on Dance Exercises in terms of Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

Attitude On Dance Exercises (Social Dance)		Mean	Interpretation
1	I find Latin and standard dances to be interesting and elegant.	3.46	Highly Positive Attitude
2	I believe learning social dances helps build confidence and discipline.	3.48	Highly Positive Attitude
3	I enjoy participating in ballroom and social dances.	3.31	Highly Positive Attitude
4	I find dancing Latin and standard dances beneficial to my physical health.	3.39	Highly Positive Attitude
5	I believe social dances can contribute to better mental health.	3.44	Highly Positive Attitude
Category Mean		3.42	Highly Positive Attitude

As shown in Table 3, students have a highly positive attitude toward Dance exercises, specifically Social Dances (Latin and Standard), as indicated in the following statements: learning social dances helps build confidence and discipline. (M=3.48) I find Latin and standard dances interesting and elegant. (M=3.46) I believe social dances can contribute to better mental health. (M= 3.44) I find dancing Latin and standard dances beneficial to my physical health. (M=3.39) I enjoy participating in ballroom and social dances. (M =3.31). With a category mean of 3.42, this implies that students demonstrate

a highly positive attitude toward dance exercises, specifically Social Dances (Latin and Standard).

Part 3. Practices of College Students on Dance Exercises

3.1 Philippine Folkdance

Table 4
Practices on dance exercises in terms of Philippine Folk dance

	Practice On Dance Exercises (Philippine Folkdance)	Mean	Interpretation
1	I participate in folk dance practices or performances.	3.12	Often Practiced
2	I attend folk dance-related activities or events.	2.97	Often Practiced
3	I have taken a course or lesson involving Philippine folk dances.	2.97	Often Practiced
4	I watch folk dance performances (online or live).	2.98	Often Practiced
5	I practice folk dance routines even outside of school.	2.72	Often Practiced
6	I perform folk dances to help me reduce stress and improve my mood.	2.81	Often Practiced
7	I perform a folk dance to increase mental alertness and focus.	2.89	Often Practiced
Category Mean		2.92	Often Practiced

As reflected in Table 4, students often practiced participating in folk dance practices or performances. (M=3.12); watching folk dance performances (online or live) (M=2.98); attending folk dance-related activities or events. (M=2.97); taking a course or lesson involving Philippine folk dances. (M=2.97); performing a folk dance to increase mental alertness and focus. (M=2.89); performing folk dances to help me reduce stress and improve my mood. (M=2.81); practicing folk dance routines even outside of school. (M=2.72). With a category mean of 2.92, students often practiced dance exercises, specifically folk dance.

3.2 Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

Table 5
Practices on dance exercises in terms of Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

	Practice on Dance Exercises (Social Dances)	Mean	Interpretation
1	I participate in social dance practices or events.	3.00	Often Practiced
2	I have taken ballroom dance classes.	2.58	Often Practiced
3	I dance Latin or standard ballroom dances during social gatherings.	2.60	Often Practiced
4	I rehearse social dance steps in my free time.	2.65	Often Practiced
5	I actively seek opportunities to improve my social dancing skills.	2.82	Often Practiced
6	I participate in social dance to enhance my cardiovascular fitness and stamina.	2.84	Often Practiced
7	I dance Latin or standard ballroom to relieve anxiety and enhance my emotional well-being.	2.76	Often Practiced
Category Mean		2.75	Often Practiced

As reflected in Table 5, students often practiced participating in social dance practices or events. (M=3.00); participating in social dance to enhance my cardiovascular fitness and stamina. (M=2.84); actively seeking opportunities to improve my social dancing skills. (M=2.82); dancing Latin or standard ballroom relieves anxiety and enhances my emotional well-being. (M=2.76); rehearsing social dance steps in my free time. (M=2.65); dancing Latin or standard ballroom dances during social gatherings. (M=2.60); taking ballroom dance classes. (M=2.58). With a category mean of 2.75, students often practiced dance exercises, specifically social dances (Latin and Standard).

Part 4. Proposed measures in Promoting Active Training and Holistic Fitness (PATHFIT) Through Interactive Dance Exercise to enhance college students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices on dance exercises (Philippine Folkdance and Social Dances)

Title: Promoting Active Training and Holistic Fitness (PATHFIT) Through Interactive Dance Exercise

Program Rationale

Based on the findings, most college students demonstrated adequate knowledge in Philippine folk dance (49.5%) and Social Dances (35.5%). However, a notable proportion reported having basic or minimal knowledge, particularly in Social Dances, where 14.0% reported minimal understanding.

While students expressed a highly positive attitude toward Philippine Folkdance (mean = 3.50) and Social Dances (mean = 3.42), actual practice levels were relatively low, with only 2.92 and 2.75 mean scores, respectively.

This gap between knowledge/attitude and actual practice calls for a dynamic, structured program that encourages more frequent, engaging, and educational dance activities.

Component	Objective	Strategy (Key Activities)	Human Resources & Budget	Success Indicators	Timeline
1. Pre-Program Preparation	To prepare schedules, partnerships, resources for smooth implementation	-Orientation with PE instructors, Salettianian Dance Troupe(SDT), Young Physical Educators Club (YPEC), and Culture & Arts Office - Finalization of schedules and integration of PATHFIT activities - Preparation of instructional materials (e.g., slides, music, dance literature)	PE Instructors, SDT, YPEC officers Budget: ₱2,000 (materials)	- Finalized calendar and class integration - Signed collaboration agreements - Attendance sheets & planning reports	Weeks 1–3, 2nd Semester
2. Knowledge Deepening	To enhance students' understanding of dance exercises (Philippine Folkdance and Social Dances)	- Classroom discussions on dance history and cultural relevance - Workshops with costume and props use (with SDT) - Viewing and analysis of dance videos and step demonstrations	PE Instructors, SDT, Students Budget: ₱3,000 (facilitator food)	-Increase in the number of students progressing from minimal, basic, and adequate knowledge to superior. -Results from their post-program knowledge test show that 90% or more of the students score in	Weeks 7–17

				the Superior knowledge bracket (9-10 points out of 10) for each component: Philippine folkdance and Social Dances. - Quality of quiz and worksheet outputs	
3. Attitude Enrichment	To develop positive attitudes toward dance and cultural fitness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer reflections and sharing sessions - Small group presentations on dance meanings and values 	PE Instructors, YPEC, Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Average attitude score from the Likert-scale attitude survey is 3.7 or above. -At least 80% of the students indicate agree or strongly agree on key positive statements about dance exercise. Attitude mean score \geq 3.7 - 80% agree/strongly agree on key survey items 	Weeks 7–18
4. Practice Development	To promote regular dance exercise participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In-class participation in dance routines - Peer-led practices and mentoring - Midterm and final group dance presentations 	Students, PE Instructors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Average practice frequency score from post-program survey is between 3.25 and 4.00. -At least 85% of students report practicing dance weekly or more during PATHFIT classes. 	Weeks 9–12 & 15–18

5. Student Engagement Activities	To encourage collaboration, performance, and student creativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interclass dance exercise contest - Culminating performance or showcase - Coordination with SDT and YPEC 	PE Instructors, Students, YPEC Officers Budget: ₱5,000 (materials & tokens)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contest participation and attendance - Improved peer collaboration and performance quality 	Weeks 12 & 18
6. Culminating Activity and Evaluation	To assess outcomes and recognize student development in knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final class dance performances - Post-KAP surveys and knowledge test - Collection of student reflections and feedback 	PE Instructors, YPEC Officers, Students		

DISCUSSION

The Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) assessment is a valuable tool in evaluating the preparedness of students to adopt and maintain behaviors that support active participation in dance exercises. In the context of the study, which focuses on Philippine folk dance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard), the KAP framework offers valuable insights into students' existing levels of knowledge, attitudes toward these dance forms, and actual engagement in related practices. Before implementing an intervention, conducting a KAP assessment allows the identification of gaps, refinement of attitudes, and the development of effective strategies that lead to greater involvement in dance-based exercise. The KAP evaluation ensures that planned and proposed programs are carefully designed, targeted, and aligned with the student population's specific needs and readiness, enhancing the instruction and promotion of dance exercises.

I. Level of Knowledge on Dance Exercises in Terms of Philippine Folkdance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

The study findings revealed that college students generally have adequate knowledge of dance exercises, particularly in Philippine folk dances and Social Dances (Latin and Standard). Most students demonstrated adequate knowledge of dance exercises, particularly Philippine folk dance. Most students demonstrated adequate knowledge of dance exercises, particularly social dances (Latin and Standard). These results suggest that students possess a foundational understanding of dance exercise.

This supports the study of Chen (2023), who emphasized that folkdance education enhances students' personal and cultural development. However, some students have minimal knowledge of social dance. This is consistent with the findings of Javina (2021) and Reyes et al. (2020), who noted that while dance is integrated into curricula, many students lack in-depth knowledge and cultural appreciation due to limited exposure and actual performance experience. Therefore, despite promising levels of general knowledge, these findings indicate the need for more immersive and hands-on dance education, especially in social dance.

II. Attitudes of College Students on Dance Exercises in terms of Philippine Folk dance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

The result indicates that college students exhibit a highly positive attitude toward dance exercises in Philippine folk and social dances. Students strongly agreed that folk dance is a valuable form of physical activity that plays an important part in Filipino culture, contributes to health and fitness, and fosters a sense of pride. Similarly, students acknowledged that social dances promote confidence and discipline, which are beneficial for physical and mental well-being.

These findings align with the studies of Mohamed et al. (2022), Sharma et. al. (2023), and Maduakolam et al. (2023), who reported that students generally maintain favorable attitudes toward physical activity and exercise. Moreover, Lobo (2022) and Monte (2025) affirmed that positive attitudes are often linked to cultural appreciation and personal interest, especially when students are exposed to dance experiences. However, the study of Hsu et al. (2023) shows that positive attitudes can be further strengthened through engaging and interactive dance instruction that emphasizes creativity, cultural storytelling, and props. This implies that continuous and innovative instruction must support the highly positive attitudes to sustain interest and participation.

III. Practices of College students on Dance Exercises in terms of Philippine Folk dance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard)

Despite the highly positive attitudes and adequate knowledge, college students often practiced dance exercises in Philippine folk and social dances. While this level of engagement is encouraging, it also reveals a gap between students' adequate knowledge and highly positive attitudes and their actual behavior or practice. This gap mirrors the findings of Reyes et al (2020) and Lobo et al. (2022), who emphasized limited student participation in traditional dance activities despite high cultural regard. This is also further supported by Moore et al. (2023), who pointed to barriers such as academic pressure, time constraints, and low prioritization of physical activity among college students. These factors likely contribute to the reduced frequency of practice found in the study. Moreover, while Latin dance has been proven to offer substantial health benefits such as improved cardiovascular fitness and mental health (Isath et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023), students may not consistently engage in such practices without accessible, structured, and motivating dance programs.

Conclusions

The study assessed college students' Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) regarding dance exercises, particularly Philippine folk dance and Social Dances (Latin and Standard). The findings revealed these insights:

Most college students demonstrated adequate to superior knowledge of dance exercises in Philippine folk dance and social dances. This level of awareness suggests that cultural and curricular exposure effectively contributes to student understanding. However, a considerable percentage of students remain within the minimal to basic knowledge bracket, which implies a gap that must be addressed. Despite promising levels of general knowledge, these findings indicate the need for more immersive and hands-on dance education, especially in social dance.

College students generally showed a highly positive attitude toward dance exercises. These results affirm the role of dance in promoting cultural identity, discipline, physical, mental, and emotional well-being. The positive attitude is a strong foundation for increasing student participation in dance activities. This implies that continuous and innovative instruction must support the highly positive attitudes to sustain interest and participation.

While students often engaged in dance-related activities and exercises, the practice level was lower than their knowledge and attitudes. The folk dance and social dance practices suggest that dance is practiced, but not consistently. This gap implies a need for structured, engaging programs that reinforce dance practice as a regular part of students' physical activity.

A noticeable gap exists between what students know and feel about dance exercises and how frequently they engage in them. This implies the importance of interventions that teach and motivate students to include dance as a lifestyle component.

Recommendations

To address the identified gap, the Promoting Active Training and Holistic Fitness (PATHFIT) Through Interactive Dance Exercise program was proposed to enhance KAP by integrating cultural learning, skill development, physical engagement, and collaborative activities and performance into the PATHFIT course.

Based on the findings and the proposed intervention, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To enhance the level of knowledge of college students on dance exercise:
 - 1.1. Integrate the Promoting Active Training and Holistic Fitness (PATHFIT) Through Interactive Dance Exercise program into the Physical Education Curriculum to strengthen students' conceptual and practical knowledge of

- Philippine Folkdance and social Dances. The structured content that includes dance histories, forms, and styles will enrich students' understanding.
- 1.2. Instructors should include the cultural and historical background when teaching the different dances. Highlight that these dances are also a form of physical activity and exercise they can engage in.
 - 1.3. Integrate interactive and multimedia resources, such as tutorials, performance videos, and gamified assessments, to make learning more engaging and accessible.
2. To sustain and cultivate a positive attitude of students toward dance exercises:
 - 2.1. Provide reflection activities and value-based discussions to allow students to explore the personal, cultural, and health benefits of engaging in Philippine folk dance and Social dances.
 - 2.2. Conduct peer-sharing and collaborative learning activities to let the students express how these dances connect to their identity, wellness, and community.
 - 2.3. Recognize and reward students' participation and improvement to reinforce positive emotional and motivational association with dancing.
 3. To improve the practice and actual engagement of the students in dance exercise:
 - 3.1. Promote consistency in practice through performance-based assessments like recitals, interclass competitions, and creative project-based learning, making dance a visible and regular component of students' routine.
 - 3.2. Reinforce regular dance practice by integrating structured in-class drills, peer-led sessions, and challenge-based dance activities in Philippine folk and social dances.
 - 3.3. Extend opportunities beyond class hours by organizing student-led workshops and school-wide dance activities to promote a culture of movement and community involvement.
 4. To propose and support the implementation of a comprehensive program to enhance KAP in dance exercises:
 - 4.1. Adopt the Promoting Active Training and Holistic Fitness (PATHFIT) Through Interactive Dance Exercise program, a student-centered intervention that combines knowledge-building, attitude development, and skill-based practice.
 - 4.2. Collaborate with the different student organizations and cultural groups to enrich the dance exercise program with shared resources and technical inputs.
 - 4.3. Monitor and evaluate the program to ensure relevance and effectiveness based on students' feedback and learning outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adhered to ethical standards concerning privacy and data protection. The researcher ensured that all respondents were treated with anonymity. All

responses were used solely for academic purposes and were handled with the utmost confidentiality. Before data collection, participants were presented with an informed consent that clearly explained the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their rights as respondents. They were assured that their participation was voluntary. All procedures conformed to the institutional research ethics guidelines, and the study was conducted with integrity and respect. Furthermore, the researcher acknowledges the use of AI tools, such as OpenAI's ChatGPT and Grammarly, to assist in information search and grammar polishing, thereby improving the flow and clarity of the text. Nevertheless, it is assured that all decisions, results, and ideas were made and collated by the author, and any content provided by the mentioned AI tools was reviewed and verified before being included in this study.

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